

EFFICIENCY OF USING MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

Absalamov Khiloliddin¹, Tojiyeva Mashxura Navruz qizi²

¹Academic supervisor

²Samarkand state institute of foreign languages
2nd course

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Abstract: The article discusses real life benefits of using modern technologies in primary schools.

Keywords: modern media, the variety of lessons in schools, innovative technologies, non-traditional education, elementary education.

Преимущества использования современных информационных технологий в обучении в начальных классах.

Аннотация: В статье обсуждаются реальные преимущества использования современных технологий в начальных школах.

Ключевые слова: Современные медиа, разнообразие уроков в школах, инновационные технологии, нетрадиционное образование, начальное образование.

In our century is the century of information technology all over the world, we cannot imagine any industry without modern information technology. We need to inform primary school students about information technology in particular and use conventional modern media in the classroom. Especially this method is very effective in learning and teaching foreign languages. At present, great demands are made on students and schoolchildren, all of them are aimed at educating the younger generation, it is necessary to study and teach. The most important of the requirements is the effectiveness of the lesson, its quality depends on the knowledge and skills of students, the variety of lessons in schools, their organization, and through them students acquire different knowledge and skills. In addition to the study sessions, organizing and encouraging various student competitions during academic months is also a great way to encourage students to study. Today, the role of innovative technologies, technical means, including modern computers, in the correct and efficient organization of the educational process is invaluable. Even a teacher with 40 years of experience will not be able to effectively convey a topic to students if they enter a 40-minute lesson without preparation. Therefore, the use of multimedia, animation, graphics, slides and videos, motivational videos, cartoons on each topic of the lesson will always make the lesson process more interesting, for which the teacher will have to work hard on himself or herself and enter each lesson with some kind of innovation, always

asking themselves that what I do in class today will be more interesting and productive than anything else. This method is the best way to move from traditional education to non-traditional education. This method also dramatically increases the ability to think logically. Non-traditional learning makes the lesson different from everyday lessons, interesting, effective and, of course, helps all students to actively participate in the learning process. We know that education is a joint activity of a teacher and students, through which the teacher tries to transfer his knowledge, skills and abilities to students through lessons, but this is not their goal. But they should never allow this move to be one-sided, that is, they should also expect excellent results from students. If there are no results, then the teacher will have to change his methods to effective teaching methods. We all know that almost all secondary schools in the country, even in remote areas, are equipped with modern computers and telecommunications. This, in turn, requires new approaches to elementary school students' own work activities. That is, every student should know how to use them effectively, to use them freely. The introduction of new technologies in the primary school curriculum transforms teaching activities into a more diverse, creative and creative profession, changing the task and role of the student through a new approach, rather than squeezing the student by technical means. . The teacher can perform the following tasks using modern computer technology:

- encourage primary school students to study science using multimedia technologies;
- improving the effectiveness of students' learning through the use of various modern teaching materials;
- development of thinking skills;
- concentration;
- development of IT skills;
- increase creativity.

At present, the demand for the use of interactive methods and information technology in any educational process in modern education is growing. One of the reasons for the increase in such demands was that before the pandemic all over the world, students in traditional education had only ready knowledge, during the pandemic all students used modern technologies, searched for knowledge, taught to think independently, analyze, and study, and even draw their own conclusions. Overall, the use of modern information and communication technologies in the primary grades helps students to think independently, expand their creative research and logical thinking, as well as connect what they learn in class with life and increase their interest in the lesson.

Effective use of the conditions created by such modern requirements of students, the organization of lessons on the basis of advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies guarantees the quality of the educational process.

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